

1 **Secretory pathway mobilization in the human embryo during lineage specification.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We report here mobilization of the
9 secretory pathway during TE lineage commitment embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

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